

History and development of English children's literature

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The future of any nation and country depends on its young successors and, of course, how developed their thinking is. Literature, which is the main tool that teaches people to think and think, has not lost its place even in the 21st century, which is considered the age of fast information and high technologies.

Literature can be divided into two - adult and children's literature, depending on the age group of readers. As a separate part of general literature, children's literature is also an art of words.

Children's literature is a set of artistic, scientific, scientific-popular and journalistic works created for children and teenagers. The main part of these are artistic works. The fiction literature of the peoples of the world begins with examples of oral creativity, most of which are intended for children, such as quick sayings, riddles, game songs, narratives, legends, fairy tales, proverbs, parables, and epics. Examples of children's and youth literature can be divided into the following groups:

- 1) samples of children's folk art;
- 2) works created directly for children;
- 3) works that were not originally intended for children, but later became children's literature.

The unique feature of children's literature is a changing phenomenon, which is directly related to the reader's age, historical period and social environment. Considering the age of the reader is one of the main features of children's literature. For example, in children of preschool age, this exhibitionism is based on

the seemingly simple conflicts of the forces of goodness and evil, while the psyche of complex people in complex life begins to open up in the literature created for teenagers.

Another feature of children's literature is its richness of action. From this comes the demand for the plot in children's literature. It requires quick, interesting, imaginative, humorous resolution of events. Children prefer short and fast-paced stories to long images and explanations. "What will happen now?" This question is one of the most interesting questions for any reading child.

For a work created for children, writers choose a topic based on the children's point of view and their psychology. Also, the language of the work is grammatically simple and understandable, based on children's daily speech. If the speech of adults is used in the work, it will tire the children, and despite the interesting plot, the children will get bored quickly.

Another feature of children's literature is the age of the characters. Children who read books are more interested in the adventures of their peers than the adult hero and his instructions.

In children's literature, along with art, enlightenment also takes a leading place. Because examples of children's literature also serve to educate young people in the spirit of human qualities. The development principles of children's literature of all periods are reflected, first of all, in enlightenment and education. The formation of children's literature in almost all nations is closely related to the Enlightenment and reforms of the school-education system. Its main goal is to educate children, to develop their aesthetic consciousness and to form their worldview.

The concept of children's literature is a phenomenon that arose in the recent past, and its history and development is related to the concept of childhood and the place of children in society. The attitude of adults to children has always

influenced children's literature. If we look at children's literature as a literature that "means not the subject or the author, but the audience of readers", then it is no exaggeration to say that children's literature was created in the 18th century.

Although works for children were not written until the 18th century, folktales, songs, poems and short sayings created in folklore were intended for the children's audience. The French historian Philippe Ares writes in his work "Centuries of childhood" published in 1962 that a new interpretation of the concept of "childhood" has emerged in these days, and until the recent past, the treatment of children was almost no different from that of adults. As a proof of his opinion, he shows that until the 18th century, almost no work was written for children except for the educational writings of priests such as Venerable Bede and Elfric Eynsham. However, it is worth mentioning that other works devoted to religious education and etiquette were widespread among the children of rich families in the Middle Ages.

Harvey Darton, a scientist who has done a lot of outstanding work in the field of children's literature and history, says about the history of English children's literature: the number of such books was limited in the 17th century itself. Although there are many textbooks, as well as books of advice on the rules of behavior, none of them make children feel the pleasure of reading, on the contrary, they only feel the task ahead of them and the fear of making mistakes caused. Only in the middle of the 18th century, children's books separated from the invisible layer of English literature as a separate, independent literature".

A few centuries before the publication of children's books appeared in Britain, illustrated pamphlets depicting fairy tales and legends were considered children's favorite books. Illustrated brochures were the most bought and read books by children until the 18th century.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

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